

Non-Syndromic Familial Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma: Early Onset and Multifocal Presentation in a mother and Daughter – A Case Report and Updated Literature Review

K. Gorgi^{1*} and M. Chaouche²

¹Department of Endocrinology, CHP of Tata, Morocco

²Department of Dermatology, Mohammed VI University Hospital, Agadir, Morocco

WebLog Open Access Publications
Article ID : wjed.2026.c2702
Author : Khaoula Gorgi

OPEN ACCESS

*Correspondence:

Khaoula Gorgi, Department of Endocrinology, CHP TATA, Morocco, Tel: 0615591874;

E-mail: khaoulagorgi@gmail.com

Received Date: 01 Mar 2026

Accepted Date: 25 Mar 2026

Published Date: 27 Mar 2026

Citation:

Gorgi K, Chaouche M. Non-Syndromic Familial Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma: Early Onset and Multifocal Presentation in a mother and Daughter – A Case Report and Updated Literature Review. *WebLog J Endocrinol Diabetes*. wjed.2026.c2702. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19317524>

Copyright© 2026 Khaoula Gorgi. This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract

Introduction: Familial non-medullary thyroid carcinoma accounts for 3-7% of differentiated thyroid cancers. It is defined by the occurrence of papillary thyroid carcinoma in at least two first-degree relatives in the absence of a known hereditary syndrome.

Case Presentation: We report the case of a 56-year-old mother and her 35-year-old daughter, both diagnosed with papillary thyroid carcinoma discovered in EU-TIRADS V classified nodules. Histopathological examination revealed multifocal follicular-variant papillary microcarcinomas in the mother and an infiltrative papillary microcarcinoma in the daughter.

Conclusion: Non-syndromic familial papillary thyroid carcinoma may present with earlier onset and multifocal disease. Careful family history assessment and targeted screening of first-degree relatives may allow diagnosis at an early stage.

Keywords: Familial Papillary Carcinoma; Non-Medullary Thyroid Cancer; Multifocality; Family Screening

Introduction

Papillary Thyroid Carcinoma (PTC) accounts for more than 80% of differentiated thyroid cancers, with a continuously increasing global incidence [1].

Familial aggregation is observed in 3-7% of cases [2]. Familial Non-Medullary Thyroid Carcinoma (FNMTTC) is defined by the occurrence of thyroid cancer derived from follicular cells in at least two first-degree relatives, in the absence of an identified hereditary syndrome [3].

Several genetic syndromes may be associated with differentiated thyroid carcinoma, including Cowden syndrome, familial adenomatous polyposis, Carney Complex, and Werner syndrome [3].

Non-syndromic FNMTTC is suspected to follow an autosomal dominant inheritance pattern with incomplete penetrance [4]. Some studies suggest a more aggressive presentation compared to sporadic forms, with higher rates of multifocality and increased lymph node involvement [5, 6].

We report a mother–daughter case illustrating this entity.

Case Presentation

Case 1

A 56-year-old woman with no known family history at the time of diagnosis.

Neck ultrasound revealed an 18-mm hypoechoic nodule in the left thyroid lobe classified as EU-TIRADS V. Total thyroidectomy was performed.

Histopathological examination revealed:

- Three papillary microcarcinomas
- Follicular variant
- Stage: pT2NxMx

Postoperative course was uneventful.

Case 2

Her 35-year-old daughter underwent screening following her mother's diagnosis.

Ultrasound revealed a 13.5-mm isthmic nodule classified as EU-TIRADS V.

Total thyroidectomy was performed.

Histology concluded:

- Infiltrative papillary microcarcinoma
- Stage: pT1aNxMx

Clinical outcome was favorable.

Discussion

Definition and Diagnostic Threshold

The diagnosis of FNMTTC is based on the presence of at least two affected first-degree relatives [2].

However, true hereditary transmission is considered more likely when three or more family members are involved [7].

Genetic Basis

Unlike medullary thyroid carcinoma associated with RET mutations, no single causative gene has been identified in FNMTTC.

Susceptibility loci have been proposed (2q21, 19p13), suggesting polygenic inheritance [4, 8].

Somatic mutations such as BRAF V600E, common in sporadic forms, are also found in familial cases without a clearly distinctive pattern [9].

Clinical Aggressiveness

Several meta-analyses have shown that familial PTC is associated with:

- Higher multifocality
- Increased bilaterality
- More frequent lymph node involvement
- Higher recurrence risk [5, 6]

However, no significant difference in disease-specific mortality has been demonstrated [10].

Therapeutic Implications

According to the 2015 American Thyroid Association guidelines [11], management of differentiated thyroid cancer is based on risk stratification.

Although no specific recommendations are dedicated to familial forms, some authors suggest a more extensive approach including total thyroidectomy and closer follow-up [5].

Family Screening

The benefit of systematic ultrasound screening remains debated.

Charkes estimated that when only two family members are affected, a significant proportion may represent coincidental aggregation [7].

Nevertheless, several recent reviews support targeted screening of first-degree relatives, particularly in cases of early onset [8].

In our case, screening allowed diagnosis at the microcarcinoma stage.

Conclusion

Non-syndromic familial papillary thyroid carcinoma remains a rare entity.

It may present with earlier onset and multifocal disease. Systematic family history assessment and individualized screening strategies could improve early diagnosis.

References

1. Sung H, Ferlay J, Siegel RL, Laversanne M, Soerjomataram I, Jemal A, et al. Global Cancer Statistics 2020. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2021; 71(3): 209-249.
2. Capezzone M, Marchisotta S, Cantara S, Busonero G, Brilli L, Pazaitou-Panayiotou K, et al. Familial non-medullary thyroid carcinoma. *Endocr Relat Cancer.* 2008; 15(4): 1075-1081.
3. Guilmette J, Nosé V. Hereditary and familial thyroid tumors. *Histopathology.* 2018; 72(1): 70-81.
4. Robenshtok E, Tzvetov G, Grozinsky-Glasberg S, Shraga-Slutsky I, Weinstein R, Lazar L, et al. Clinical characteristics and outcome of familial nonmedullary thyroid cancer: a retrospective controlled study. *Thyroid.* 2011; 21(1): 43-48.
5. Liu C. Familial papillary thyroid carcinoma: meta-analysis. *Thyroid.* 2017.
6. Zhang Y. Familial versus sporadic PTC: systematic review. *Int J Surg.* 2019.
7. Charkes ND. On the prevalence of familial nonmedullary thyroid cancer in multiply affected kindreds. *Thyroid.* 2006; 16(2): 181-186.
8. Khan MS, et al. Genetics of familial non-medullary thyroid carcinoma. *Cancers.* 2020.
9. Xing M. BRAF mutation in thyroid cancer. *Endocr Relat Cancer.* 2005; 12(2): 45-62.
10. Alsanea O. Impact of familiarity on thyroid cancer outcome. *Ann Surg Oncol.* 2000.
11. Haugen BR, Alexander EK, Bible KC, Doherty GM, Mandel SJ, Nikiforov YE, et al. 2015 American Thyroid Association Management Guidelines for Adult Patients with Thyroid Nodules and Differentiated Thyroid Cancer: The American Thyroid Association Guidelines Task Force on Thyroid Nodules and Differentiated Thyroid Cancer. *Thyroid.* 2016; 26(1): 1-133.